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Cross-continental importance of CH₄ emissions from dry inland-waters

--Manuscript Draft--

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Abstract:	<p>Despite substantial advances in quantifying greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from dry inland waters, existing estimates mainly consist of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions. However, methane (CH₄) may also be relevant due to its higher Global Warming Potential (GWP). We report CH₄ emissions from dry inland water sediments to i) provide a cross-continental estimate of such emissions for different types of aquatic systems (i.e., lakes, ponds, reservoirs, and streams) and climate zones (i.e., tropical, continental, and temperate); and ii) determine the environmental factors that control these emissions. CH₄ emissions from dry inland waters were consistently higher than emissions observed in adjacent uphill soils, across climate zones and in all aquatic systems except for streams. However, the CH₄ contribution (normalized to CO₂ equivalents; CO₂-eq) to the total GHG emissions of dry inland waters was similar for all types of aquatic systems and varied from 10 – 21%. Although we discuss multiple controlling factors, dry inland water CH₄ emissions were most strongly related to sediment organic matter content and moisture. Summing CO₂ and CH₄ emissions revealed a cross-continental average emission of $9.6 \pm 17.4 \text{ g CO}_2\text{-eq m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ from dry inland waters. We argue that increasing droughts likely expand the worldwide surface area of atmosphere-exposed aquatic sediments, thereby increasing global dry inland water CH₄ emissions. Hence, CH₄ cannot be ignored if we want to fully understand the carbon (C) cycle of dry sediments.</p>
Response to Reviewers:	<p>November 19th, 2021 Science of the Total Environment Editorial Office Manuscript ID: STOTEN-D-21-22642 Dear Dr. Qilin Wang, Please find our detailed response to each of the comments below. The italicized sentences represent the reviewer's comments, and the references to page and line numbers in our responses refer to the document named "Revised manuscript with changes marked". We also attached a clean version of the manuscript with all edits accepted (named "Revised manuscript with no changes marked"). We further improved the writing of the manuscript by making minor edits and adjusting Equation 1, all according to comments made by reviewer #3. Thank you very much for your kind support. On behalf of the co-authors, José Reinaldo Paranaíba</p> <p>REVIEWER'S COMMENTS TO AUTHORS:</p> <p>Reviewer #3 The author has responded well to the questions, but the following questions remain. 1. The author needs to pay attention to the tense of the whole text. For example, the description of the research citing other existing literatures should be in the past tense.</p> <p>Response: We went through the text and changed the writing accordingly. Please, see page 16, line 369; line 372; line 377; page 20, line 436.</p> <p>2. Line 211: Formula 1: It is hoped that the author will set the numerator and denominator of the formula into the upper and lower structure, which will not easily cause the misunderstanding of the formula, especially, (V / R^*T^*A).</p> <p>Response: Thank you for pointing this out. We have now adjusted the Equation 1 accordingly. Please, see page 10, lines 212-213.</p>

Cross-continental importance of CH₄ emissions from dry inland-waters

José. R. Paranaíba^{a,b}✉, Ralf Aben^b, Nathan Barros^a, Gabrielle Quadra^a, Annika Linkhorst^{c,d}, André M. Amado^{a,e}, Soren Brothers^f, Núria Catalán^g, Jason Condon^h, Colin M. Finlaysonⁱ, Hans-Peter Grossart^{j,k}, Julia Howitt^{l,†}, Ernandes S. Oliveira Junior^m, Philipp S. Kellerⁿ, Matthias Koschorreckⁿ, Alo Laas^o, Catherine Leigh^p, Rafael Marcé^{r,s}, Raquel Mendonça^a, Claumir C. Muniz^m, Biel Obrador^t, Gabriela Onandia^{u,v}, Diego Raymundo^x, Florian Reverej^u, Fábio Roland^a, Eva-Ingrid Rõõm^{o,w}, Sebastian Sobek^c, Daniel von Schiller^t, Haijun Wang^y, Sarian Kosten^b

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32 [†] – *In memoriam*
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64 **Graphical abstract**

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79 **Abstract**

80 Despite substantial advances in quantifying greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from dry
81 inland waters, existing estimates mainly consist of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions.
82 However, methane (CH₄) may also be relevant due to its higher Global Warming
83 Potential (GWP). We report CH₄ emissions from dry inland water sediments to i)
84 provide a cross-continental estimate of such emissions for different types of aquatic
85 systems (i.e., lakes, ponds, reservoirs, and streams) and climate zones (i.e., tropical,
86 continental, and temperate); and ii) determine the environmental factors that control
87 these emissions. CH₄ emissions from dry inland waters were consistently higher than
88 emissions observed in adjacent uphill soils, across climate zones and in all aquatic
89 systems except for streams. However, the CH₄ contribution (normalized to CO₂
90 equivalents; CO₂-eq) to the total GHG emissions of dry inland waters was similar for all
91 types of aquatic systems and varied from 10 – 21%. Although we discuss multiple
92 controlling factors, dry inland water CH₄ emissions were most strongly related to
93 sediment organic matter content and moisture. Summing CO₂ and CH₄ emissions
94 revealed a cross-continental average emission of 9.6 ± 17.4 g CO₂-eq m⁻² d⁻¹ from dry
95 inland waters. We argue that increasing droughts likely expand the worldwide surface
96 area of atmosphere-exposed aquatic sediments, thereby increasing global dry inland
97 water CH₄ emissions. Hence, CH₄ cannot be ignored if we want to fully understand the
98 carbon (C) cycle of dry sediments.

99 **Keywords:** Methane; Dry sediments; Aquatic ecosystems; Greenhouse gases;

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102 **1. Introduction**

103 Inland waters (e.g., lakes, ponds, reservoirs, rivers) are complex ecosystems that
104 process large amounts of allochthonous and autochthonous organic matter (Attermeyer
105 et al., 2017; Clair and Ehrman, 1996; Friedl and Wüest, 2002; Van Cappellen and
106 Maavara, 2016) and play important roles as sources and sinks within the global C cycle
107 (Cole et al., 2007; Rosentreter et al., 2021; Tranvik et al., 2009). In aquatic ecosystems,
108 organic matter undergoes various biogeochemical processes, including its
109 decomposition into gaseous carbon (C) species (Mattson and Likens, 1992) such as
110 carbon dioxide (CO₂) and methane (CH₄) (Bastviken et al., 2011; DelSontro et al.,
111 2018; Raymond et al., 2013). In addition, part of the organic matter can settle and
112 accumulate in sediments (Heathcote et al., 2015; Mendonça et al., 2017). According to
113 C-budget studies, approximately 0.06–0.25 Pg C y⁻¹ are estimated to be buried in
114 sediments of inland waters worldwide (Anderson et al., 2020; Mendonça et al., 2017),
115 whereas approximately 3.9 Pg C y⁻¹ are emitted from inland waters to the atmosphere as
116 CO₂ and as CH₄ (Drake et al., 2018).

117 After CO₂, CH₄ is the most important gas contributing to the global greenhouse
118 effect. Considering the Global Warming Potential (GWP) over a 100-year time horizon,
119 one gram of CH₄ exerts an atmospheric heating power equivalent to 34 grams of CO₂
120 (Myhre et al., 2013). Globally, approximately 0.15 Pg of C are annually emitted from
121 freshwaters to the atmosphere as CH₄ (not considering wetlands, rice paddies and
122 aquaculture ponds). About 0.13 Pg C y⁻¹ of these emissions evade to the atmosphere
123 from lentic (non-flowing) aquatic systems such as lakes, ponds and reservoirs, and
124 ~0.02 Pg C y⁻¹ from lotic (flowing) systems such as streams and rivers (Rosentreter et
125 al., 2021). A large part of the CH₄ production in aquatic systems occurs in anoxic
126 sediments via microbial degradation of organic matter (Bastviken et al., 2004). The

127 resulting CH₄ that escapes microbial oxidation at the sediment-water interface and water
128 column (Granéli et al., 1996; Heilman and Carlton, 2001) reaches the atmosphere
129 through diffusion (Bastviken et al., 2004; Cole and Caraco, 1998), ebullition (bubbling)
130 (Bastviken et al., 2004), plant-mediated transport (Abril et al., 2005), and by the passage
131 of deep, CH₄-rich waters through the turbines of hydroelectric reservoirs (“degassing”)
132 (Abril et al., 2005; Kemenes et al., 2016). In addition, even after exposure to
133 atmospheric air, sediment CH₄ production can continue in anoxic microhabitats (Dalal
134 et al., 2008; Serrano-Silva et al., 2014). However, a large share of the CH₄ produced in
135 these micro-regions is oxidized to CO₂ by methanotrophic bacteria before evasion to the
136 atmosphere, especially during the first hours or days after atmospheric exposure
137 (Koschorreck, 2000). The remaining CH₄ may directly diffuse to the atmosphere.

138 Many inland water ecosystems worldwide experience periods of drying (Marcé
139 et al., 2019; Messenger et al., 2021). Drying can result from natural (i.e., intermittency of
140 rivers and ponds) or human-induced (i.e., human actions in reservoirs and lakes) water
141 level and flow fluctuations (Beaulieu et al., 2018; Di Baldassarre et al., 2018; Leigh et
142 al., 2016; Wurtsbaugh et al., 2017). During the dry season, considerable areas of
143 marginal aquatic sediments are exposed directly to the atmosphere. Pekel et al. (2016)
144 estimated that ~800,000 km² (or 18%) of the global surface area that is covered by
145 inland waters are subject to seasonal atmospheric exposure, especially non-flowing
146 reaches, which dominate the hydrological networks (Messenger et al., 2021). Moreover,
147 15% of the global reservoir surfaces are dry (Keller et al., 2021).

148 Exposed aquatic sediments may represent a substantial source of GHG to the
149 atmosphere (Keller et al., 2020; Marcé et al., 2019; von Schiller et al., 2014) but are
150 seldom considered in global C emission estimates. Local, regional, and global GHG
151 emission estimates from dry inland waters have emerged and improved considerably in

152 the last decade (Beaulieu et al., 2018; Gallo et al., 2014; Harrison et al., 2017; Jin et al.,
153 2016; Marcé et al., 2019), especially for CO₂ (Almeida et al., 2019; Catalán et al., 2014;
154 Deshmukh et al., 2018; Keller et al., 2020; Obrador et al., 2018; von Schiller et al.,
155 2014). Keller et al. (2020) found that 0.12 ± 0.13 Pg C y⁻¹ are added to recent global
156 inland water C emission estimates when CO₂ emissions from dry inland waters are
157 considered. However, compared to CO₂, other GHGs have been poorly assessed in
158 drying sediments, preventing a complete picture of their role in biogeochemical cycling.
159 Particularly for CH₄, the number of studies on dry inland waters is not sufficient to
160 reliably upscale CH₄ fluxes of these habitats to the global scale (Marcé et al., 2019).
161 Because of this, a recent global estimate of GHG emissions from dry reservoir
162 sediments assumed zero CH₄ emissions (Keller et al., 2021). In addition, the
163 environmental drivers regulating CH₄ fluxes from dry inland waters are not fully
164 understood. Therefore, the contribution of CH₄ emission from exposed sediments to
165 global C emission from inland waters remains to be quantified.

166 This study aims to assess the importance of CH₄ fluxes from the exposed
167 sediments of different types of aquatic systems (i.e., lakes, ponds, reservoirs, and
168 streams) located in various climate zones across the globe. To achieve this, dry inland
169 water CH₄ fluxes were i) compared to CH₄ fluxes observed in adjacent uphill (natural
170 terrestrial) soils; ii) compared to the CO₂ fluxes obtained at the same locations where
171 CH₄ fluxes were measured; iii) related to physical and chemical sediment properties that
172 were concurrently measured along with CH₄ in order to identify drivers of CH₄ fluxes
173 from exposed sediments; iv) scaled up to the respective dry global surface areas
174 associated with each type of aquatic system studied here, to v) ultimately determine
175 whether dry inland water CH₄ fluxes represent a significant share of the global C
176 emission estimates from inland waters. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first

177 cross-continental study quantifying the magnitude and environmental controls of CH₄
178 fluxes from the dry sediments of multiple aquatic system types.

179

180 2. Methods

181 2.1 Studied sites and sampling strategy

182 This study includes measurements in 89 hydrologically independent aquatic
183 systems (lakes, $n = 45$; ponds, $n = 16$; reservoirs, $n = 19$; and streams, $n = 9$), located in
184 three of the five global climate zones (tropical, $n = 24$; continental, $n = 11$; and
185 temperate, $n = 54$) (Kottek et al., 2006) (Figure 1), which were conducted by 22
186 research groups from 10 countries. The research groups were classified as levels of a
187 variable named “*research group*”, which were used in the analysis of CH₄ flux drivers
188 (see below). The 89 systems are a subset of the 196 aquatic systems included in a recent
189 global study on CO₂ emission from exposed sediments by Keller et al. (2020). The
190 subset was created based on the availability of CH₄ flux data (i.e., not all datasets
191 contained CH₄ data).

192 At each sampling site, two distinct regions were sampled: i) exposed sediment –
193 hereafter named as “*dry inland water*”, which corresponds to an area with air-exposed
194 sediment that experiences periodic and/or recent historical inundation (Marcé et al.,
195 2019); and ii) adjacent uphill soil, which corresponds to the adjacent terrestrial region
196 that is not inundated. At each region, measurements were performed in triplicates that
197 were, if possible, conducted at least 1 meter apart from each other to capture spatial
198 within-region variability.

199

200 **Figure 1** | Cross-continental distribution of the sampling sites (white dots) across the
 201 different climate zones according to the Köppen-Geiger climate classification system
 202 (Kottek et al., 2006).

203

204 **2.2 CH₄ flux measurements**

205 Between 2016 and 2017, *in situ* measurements of CH₄ flux (mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹)
 206 were conducted using opaque chambers connected to infrared gas analyzers in closed
 207 gas loops. The chambers were gently placed over the sediment/soil surface to avoid
 208 disturbance and gas leakage during the measurements, and where necessary, sealed with
 209 clay (Lesmeister and Koschorreck, 2017). Changes in CH₄ partial pressure (*m*CH₄) were

210 monitored within the chambers over 3-5 minutes, and the fluxes were calculated
211 following:

$$F_{CH_4} = (dmCH_4/dt) * (V/R*T*A) \quad (1)$$
$$\left(\frac{dmCH_4}{dt} \right) \times \left(\frac{V}{RTA} \right)$$

214 where $dmCH_4$ is the slope of change in mCH_4 (ppm) over time (dt , given in seconds), V
215 is the volume of the chamber (m^3), R is the gas constant = $8.205746 \times 10^{-5} m^3 atm mol^{-1}$
216 K^{-1} , T is the air temperature (K), and A is the surface area covered by the chamber (m^2).

217 Dry inland waters lack CH_4 ebullition as an emission route (Marcé et al., 2019),
218 mainly due to the absence of water overlying the sediments. Therefore, our
219 measurements represent only the diffusion of CH_4 at the sediment/soil-atmosphere
220 interface. Opaque chambers were used in order to minimize temperature changes during
221 measurements, which may affect the gas exchange at the interface between
222 sediment/soil and headspace (Welles et al., 2001). Chamber deployments were
223 performed on top of bare sediment/soil, avoiding vegetated surfaces.

224

225 **2.3 Sediment/soil characterization**

226 After the flux measurements, surface sediment/soil samples were collected from
227 the plot of the flux measurement, placed in plastic bags and stored in thermal cooler
228 boxes for subsequent laboratory analysis. Air and sediment/soil temperature ($^{\circ}C$) were
229 measured *in situ*, and elevation (m.a.s.l., meters above sea level) was either measured *in*
230 *situ* or read from a map. Sediment/soil texture was determined following a manipulative
231 test developed by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO,
232 2020) and distinguished as clay, light clay, heavy loam, sandy loam, loamy sand, and

233 sand. 10 g of fresh sediment/soil were mixed in 25 mL distilled water for the
234 determination of electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$) and pH by measuring the suspended
235 solution (after 1 h standing) with conventional electrodes (Keller et al., 2020). Moisture
236 content (% weight loss) was determined by drying 5 g of fresh sediment/soil at 105 °C
237 until reaching a constant weight (Keller et al., 2020). Afterward, the samples were
238 combusted at 500 °C until constant weight for the determination of the organic matter
239 content (% weight loss) (Dean, 1974).

240

241 ***2.4 Data analysis and statistical procedures***

242 Each sampling site was assigned to a climate zone according to “The World
243 Maps of Köppen-Geiger Climate Classification” (Kottek et al., 2006). For each
244 sampling site, we then calculated the contribution of dry inland water CH₄ emission to
245 the total (i.e., CO₂ + CH₄) GHG emission in CO₂-equivalents (CO₂-eq; see below how
246 CH₄ was converted to CO₂-eq) for each type of aquatic system (lakes, ponds, reservoirs,
247 and streams). The CO₂ flux data was retrieved from Keller et al. (2020), and each CO₂
248 flux measurement was associated with the CH₄ flux measurement collected at the same
249 sampling site. For all analyses, triplicate measurements were averaged, and one average
250 value per parameter at each sampling site was used.

251 To test the relationships between environmental variables and dry inland water
252 CH₄ fluxes, a generalized linear mixed model (GLMM) was performed using the
253 “*glmer*” function in the “*lme4*” package (Bates et al., 2015) in R (v. 4.0.2) (R Core
254 Team, 2018). We used sediment texture, sediment temperature, pH, electrical
255 conductivity, moisture and organic matter content, as well as latitude, elevation, annual
256 mean precipitation, and annual mean air temperature as fixed effects. Given that CH₄

257 fluxes are primarily driven by the availability and quality of organic matter, moisture,
258 and temperature (Aben et al., 2017; Grasset et al., 2018; Koschorreck, 2000; Sobek et
259 al., 2012; Yvon-Durocher et al., 2014), the interactions between i) organic matter
260 content and temperature, ii) organic matter and moisture content, and iii) moisture
261 content and temperature of the sediments were also included as fixed effects. The
262 variables research group, type of aquatic system, and climate zone were used as crossed
263 random factors to account for the dependencies in the data. We used GLMM because
264 preliminary analyses showed that the distribution of the residuals of the linear mixed
265 models followed a logarithmic distribution and, therefore, the Gamma family (*link=log*)
266 was applied in the GLMM (Lo and Andrews, 2015). A value of $13 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ was
267 added to the CH_4 flux data (i.e., $x + 13$) to avoid negative values which would hamper
268 our GLMM analysis since the Gamma family (*link=log*) does not allow negative values
269 in the response variable. The observed negative CH_4 flux values (i.e., influx; see section
270 3. Results and Discussion) were very small in magnitude compared with emissions –
271 most of the influx data were close to zero and the strongest influx was roughly 7 mg
272 $\text{CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$, whereas the efflux rates were often two orders of magnitude greater than
273 influx rates. Therefore, the addition of the fixed value aforementioned does not have a
274 relevant impact on the overall driver analysis. Logarithmic and cubic root
275 transformations were adopted for electrical conductivity and organic matter content ($x +$
276 1), moisture, and elevation, respectively, to meet the conditions of normality and
277 homoscedasticity of variances. Before analysis, collinearity between predictor variables
278 was assessed using the variance inflation factor (VIF) function in the “*usdm*” package
279 (Naimi et al., 2014) in R. Variables with VIF values > 5 (which is indicative of
280 collinearity) were excluded from the procedures (Akinwande et al., 2015). In the
281 GLMM presented here, the excluded variable was annual precipitation. The model was

282 simplified by removing non-significant predictors. GLMMs were also used to assess
283 differences in CH₄ fluxes, moisture, and organic matter content among aquatic system
284 types (fixed factor), between sampling regions (fixed factor), and between climate zones
285 (fixed factor), with the variable research group defined as a crossed random factor.
286 Type-III ANOVAs were used to test the significance of the fixed factors, with degrees
287 of freedom and *p* values calculated using the Kenward-Roger approximation (Kenward
288 and Roger, 1997) through the “*lmerTest*” and “*pbkrtest*” packages (Halekoh and
289 Højsgaard, 2014; Kuznetsova et al., 2017). Least-square means (classical Yates
290 contrasts), as well as pairwise differences, were computed by the “*ls_means*” function
291 (“*lmerTest*” package). For all statistical procedures, a *p* value < 0.05 was adopted as the
292 threshold level of statistical significance.

293 Finally, to obtain an estimate of cross-continental CH₄ emission from dry inland
294 waters, we multiplied the average CH₄ flux rate of each type of aquatic system by its
295 respective global associated desiccated surface area (for lakes, reservoirs, and ponds:
296 Marcé et al., 2019; for streams: Raymond et al., 2013), and then summed them up. Also,
297 cross-continental CH₄ emissions from dry inland waters were converted into CO₂-eq
298 emissions by using the 100-year time horizon GWP factor of 34 (Myhre et al., 2013).

299

300 **3. Results and Discussion**

301 ***3.1 Contrasting CH₄ fluxes from dry inland waters and surrounding terrestrial areas***

302 CH₄ fluxes from dry sediments of inland waters and adjacent uphill (terrestrial)
303 soils ranged from -8 to 352 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹, with a median of 0.08 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹ and
304 an interquartile range (IQR) of 4.1 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹ (mean ± standard deviation (SD): 20
305 ± 60 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹) (Figure 2). CH₄ uptake was found in 51 uphill soil regions (57%)

306 and 21 dry inland water regions (23%) (Figure 2D – see Figure 2E and F for system
307 type and climate zones). Variability of CH₄ fluxes was larger among dry inland water
308 sediments than among uphill soils (Figure 2A). Uphill sites tend to be drained/dry and
309 oxic, which represents unfavorable conditions for CH₄ production but favorable
310 conditions for CH₄ consumption (von Fischer and Hedin, 2007). On the other hand,
311 exposed inland-water sediments may sometimes be fully desiccated, showing little or no
312 CH₄ production, or waterlogged with potential anoxia supporting CH₄ production and
313 emission (Koschorreck, 2000). While CO₂ emissions from dry inland waters tend to be
314 lower than those from uphill soils (Almeida et al., 2019; Catalán et al., 2014; Jin et al.,
315 2016; Keller et al., 2020; von Schiller et al., 2014), the pattern we observed for CH₄ was
316 opposite. Average CH₄ emissions from dry inland waters were significantly higher than
317 those from adjacent uphill soils (Figure 2A; Table 1) (mean ± SD and median – IQR,
318 respectively; dry inland water: 40 ± 80 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹, and 1 – 28.4 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹;
319 uphill soil: 1 ± 4 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹, and -0.07 – 1.1 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹; GLMM: $t = -9.61$, $p <$
320 0.001). The difference in CH₄ emissions from the two different regions may be
321 attributed to differences in moisture content as well as quality and quantity of organic
322 matter (Dalal et al., 2008; Serça et al., 2016; Serrano-Silva et al., 2014). When air-
323 exposed sediments are still wet, anoxia generally prevails below the upper few
324 millimeters of the sediment (Koschorreck and Darwich, 2003), thereby sustaining CH₄
325 production. When sediments start to dry out, CH₄ production through organic matter
326 decomposition can still take place in anoxic microhabitats (Dalal et al., 2008;
327 Koschorreck, 2000; Serrano-Silva et al., 2014). As exposed sediments of inland waters
328 dry out further, newly formed fractures ease the contact of deeper sediment layers with
329 atmospheric oxygen (Fromin et al., 2010; Kosten et al., 2018; Paranaíba et al., 2020).
330 The expansion of the oxic layer in the sediment provokes changes in microbial

331 communities and their activity (Borken and Matzner, 2009; Jin et al., 2016; Rodrigo et
332 al., 1997), favoring aerobic metabolisms (e.g., CH₄ oxidation; Jäckel et al., 2001;
333 Koschorreck, 2000), and eventually leading to a reduction in CH₄ emissions (Kosten et
334 al., 2018; Paranaíba et al., 2020). Furthermore, the microbial community in water-
335 stressed sediments is expected to desiccate (Borken and Matzner, 2009; Jin et al., 2016;
336 Rodrigo et al., 1997), which can be expected to diminish the potential of CH₄
337 production likely contributing to the wide range in CH₄ fluxes from dry inland-water
338 sediments. The importance of moisture content in regulating CH₄ emission is further
339 exemplified by the mean moisture content being consistently higher in dry inland-water
340 sediments than in uphill soils across all systems globally (mean ± SD; dry inland water:
341 33.1 ± 21.4%, uphill soil: 17 ± 9.4%; GLMM: $t = -7.03$, $p < 0.001$), corresponding with
342 the generally higher CH₄ emissions from the dry inland-water sediments. Mean organic
343 matter content, however, was similar for the two regions (mean ± SD; dry inland water:
344 7.9 ± 7%, uphill soil: 8.2 ± 7.5%; GLMM: $t = 0.19$, $p = 0.84$).

345

346 ***3.2 Dry inland waters CH₄ flux variability across aquatic systems and climate zones***

347 No statistical differences in CH₄ fluxes were found between the different types
348 of dry inland water systems (GLMM, $F = 0.63$, $p = 0.59$ – see Table S1 for pairwise
349 comparisons), due to the relatively high variability among sites within each type (Figure
350 2B; Table 1). Dry inland water sediments were a source of CH₄ in almost all cases,
351 while adjacent uphill soils could be either a source or a sink of CH₄, depending on the
352 site (Figure 2E). Dry inland water CH₄ fluxes were, on average (± SD), 48 ± 91 mg CH₄
353 m⁻² d⁻¹ ($n = 45$; median – IQR: 2.3 – 48.2 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹) in lakes, 38 ± 63 mg CH₄ m⁻²
354 d⁻¹ ($n = 16$; median – IQR: 0.7 – 84 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹) in ponds, 36 ± 78 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹
355 ($n = 19$; median – IQR: 0.08 – 13.9 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹) in reservoirs, and 7 ± 17 mg CH₄

356 $\text{m}^2 \text{d}^{-1}$ ($n = 9$; median – IQR: $0.1 - 3.5 \text{ mg CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$) in streams (Figure 2B; Table 1).
357 The lower CH_4 flux rate from dry streams corresponded with their significantly lower
358 mean ($\pm \text{SD}$) moisture and organic matter content when compared to lakes, ponds and
359 reservoirs (moisture content: streams: $20 \pm 27\%$, lakes: $31 \pm 20\%$, ponds: $52 \pm 21\%$,
360 reservoirs: $27 \pm 10\%$; GLMM, $F = 6.25$, $p = 0.0006$ – see Table S2 for pairwise
361 comparisons; organic matter content: streams: $1 \pm 1\%$, lakes: $9 \pm 8\%$, ponds: $8 \pm 4\%$,
362 reservoirs: $9 \pm 6\%$; GLMM, $F = 3.48$, $p = 0.01$ – see Table S3 for pairwise
363 comparisons). In fact, dry sediments of rivers and streams tend to have less organic
364 matter content than dry sediments of lentic water bodies (Gómez-gener et al., 2015).
365 Rivers and streams are more sensitive to variations in hydrological cycles (i.e., are
366 subject to high and recurrent water stress). In addition, water flow erodes fine-grained
367 sediment, which hinders organic matter accumulation at the margins of these systems
368 (Boix-Fayos et al., 2015; Gómez-Gener et al., 2016).

369 The CH_4 fluxes presented here ~~tend were to be~~ higher than values reported for
370 individual dry inland water CH_4 -emission in earlier studies conducted in different
371 aquatic systems (Table 1). We can only speculate about the underlying reason, which
372 may be related to drier conditions or low (quality) organic matter content found in the
373 systems from earlier studies. For instance, the mean $\pm \text{SD}$ of organic matter content
374 found in 16 ephemeral streams by Gallo et al. (2014) was $3 \pm 2.7\%$, and mean $\pm \text{SD}$ dry
375 CH_4 emission was $0.4 \pm 0.5 \text{ mg CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$, which is both considerably lower than the
376 values we found.

377 The CH_4 fluxes per square meter from dry inland waters ~~tend to be were~~ lower
378 than those from surface waters reported in the literature (Table 1). This may be related
379 to lower oxygen availability in submerged sediments possibly leading to higher CH_4
380 production and lower CH_4 consumption. In addition, the littoral regions of streams and

381 reservoirs tend to be depleted in labile organic matter due to frequent water level
382 changes, which hampers the production of CH₄ in these regions (Dalal et al., 2008;
383 Serrano-Silva et al., 2014).

384 No statistical differences in dry inland water CH₄ fluxes were found between
385 climate zones (GLMM, $F = 1.41$, $p = 0.22$ – see Table S4 for pairwise comparisons),
386 again likely due to the substantial variation in fluxes within climate zones. CH₄ efflux
387 prevailed in dry inland-water sediments across climate zones, while CH₄ influx was
388 more evident in adjacent uphill soils (except for soils from tropical zones) (Figure 2F).
389 Mean (\pm SD) dry inland water CH₄ fluxes were 96 ± 128 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹ ($n = 11$;
390 median – IQR: 0.5 – 232.1 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹) in continental zones, 54 ± 77 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹
391 ($n = 24$; median – IQR: 0.08 – 87.5 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹) in tropical zones, and 22 ± 58 mg
392 CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹ ($n = 54$; median – IQR: -0.03 – 3.7 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹) in temperate zones
393 (Figure 2C). Interestingly, the highest emissions obtained in our study were observed at
394 sampling sites located in the continental zone (mean \pm SD: 352 ± 150 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹;
395 293 ± 351 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹; and 232 ± 201 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹), which ended up determining
396 the higher mean CH₄ emission attributed to continental zones. In addition, local
397 characteristics not captured in our sampling design (e.g., surrounding land use, trophic
398 state, microbial community structure, timing of atmospheric exposure) rather than
399 regional characteristics (e.g., mean annual temperature) may be responsible for both the
400 high CH₄ emission rates and the high variability observed in our measurements. Mean
401 sediment moisture content was similar among climate zones (GLMM, $F = 2.50$, $p =$
402 0.09 ; see Table S5 for pairwise comparisons). The mean moisture content (\pm SD) in dry
403 sediments was $37 \pm 22\%$ in temperate zones, $32 \pm 27\%$ in continental zones, and $25 \pm$
404 14% in tropical zones. The highest mean (\pm SD) organic matter content was observed in
405 dry sediments of tropical zones ($11 \pm 9\%$), followed by those in temperate ($7 \pm 5\%$) and

406 continental zones ($4 \pm 5\%$) (GLMM, $F = 5.37$, $p = 0.006$ – see Table S6 for pairwise
 407 comparisons).

408

409

410 **Figure 2** | Boxplot of CH_4 fluxes ($\text{mg CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$) from dry inland waters (red boxes)
 411 and adjacent uphill soils (cyan boxes) (A); in different types of aquatic systems (B); and
 412 different climate zones (C). Number of cases of CH_4 influx (yellow bars) and efflux
 413 (blue bars) from dry inland waters (DIW) and adjacent uphill soils (UPS) (D); in
 414 different types of aquatic systems (E); and different climate zones (F). In A, B and C,

415 the y-axes are presented as logarithmic scale (\log_{10}), the lines within the boxes indicate
 416 the median, the boxes delimit the 25th and 75th percentiles, and the whiskers delimit the
 417 5th and 95th percentiles.

418 **Table 1 | Upper part:** Mean \pm standard deviation of CH₄ fluxes (mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹) from
 419 dry inland waters (dry sediments) and adjacent uphill soils among lakes, ponds,
 420 reservoirs, and streams. **Middle part:** Mean \pm standard deviation of CH₄ fluxes (mg
 421 CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹) from other dry inland waters (documented in the literature). **Bottom part:**
 422 Global mean \pm standard deviation of CH₄ fluxes (mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹) from surface waters
 423 of lakes, ponds, reservoirs, and streams (documented in the literature).

System type	CH ₄ flux (mg CH ₄ m ⁻² d ⁻¹)	Reference
Lakes (n = 45)		
<i>Dry sediment</i>	48 \pm 91	
<i>Uphill soil</i>	1 \pm 5	
Ponds (n = 16)		
<i>Dry sediment</i>	38 \pm 63	
<i>Uphill soil</i>	0.3 \pm 1	
Reservoirs (n = 19)		
<i>Dry sediment</i>	36 \pm 78	This study
<i>Uphill soil</i>	2 \pm 4	
Streams (n = 9)		
<i>Dry sediment</i>	7 \pm 17	
<i>Uphill soil</i>	0.2 \pm 0.7	
All systems (n = 89)		
<i>Dry sediment</i>	40 \pm 80	
<i>Uphill soil</i>	1 \pm 4	
Lake (Brazil)	1.4 \pm 0.15 (Amazonian floodplain)	Koschorreck, 2000
Ponds (Spain)	4.8 \pm 3.8 (Dry bed)	Obrador et al. 2018
Reservoir (Brazil)	0.9 \pm 6.9 (Drawdown)	Amorim et al. 2019
Reservoir (China)	7 \pm 8.9 (Drawdown)	Chen et al. 2011
Reservoir (China)	4 \pm 1.5 (Drawdown)	Yang et al. 2012
Reservoir (China)	7.7 \pm 5 (Drawdown)	Hao et al. 2019
Reservoir (Laos)	27 \pm 36 (Drawdown)	Serça et al. 2016
Reservoir (Germany)	4.1 ^a (Drawdown)	Marcé et al. 2019
Reservoir (Germany)	7.2 ^a (Drawdown)	Marcé et al. 2019
Reservoir (Spain)	0 (Drawdown)	Marcé et al. 2019
Reservoir (Spain)	4.1 ^a (Drawdown)	Marcé et al. 2019
Reservoir (Spain)	0.3 ^a (Drawdown)	Marcé et al. 2019
Streams (United States)	0.4 \pm 0.5 (Dry river bed)	Gallo et al. 2014
Streams (Spain)	3.2 \pm 0.9 (Dry river and impoundment beds)	Gómez-Gener et al. 2015
Global CH₄ flux rates from surface waters (mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹)		

Lakes	153 ± 293	Rosentreter et al. 2021
Ponds	12 ± 30	Holgerson and Raymond 2016
Reservoirs	165 ± 369	Rosentreter et al. 2021
Streams	112 ± 425	Rosentreter et al. 2021

^a Mean values

424 3.3 Drivers of CH₄ fluxes

425 The fixed effects resulting from the GLMM modeling on dry inland water CH₄
426 fluxes explained 23% of the total variance (marginal R squared, R²m), and fixed and
427 random effects together explained 57% of the total variance (conditional R squared,
428 R²c) (Table 2). Organic matter content and the interaction between organic matter
429 content and sediment temperature were the strongest predictors of CH₄ fluxes from dry
430 inland waters ($p < 0.001$; Figure S1; Table 2), followed by moisture, conductivity ($p <$
431 0.01 ; Figure S1; Table 2), elevation and the interaction between moisture and organic
432 matter content ($p < 0.05$; Figure S1; Table 2). This suggests that local sediment
433 characteristics rather than regional characteristics such as annual mean temperature
434 drive CH₄ emissions, which agrees with findings for dry inland-water CO₂ emissions
435 (Keller et al., 2020) (Figure S1; Table 2). However, the particular drivers of CO₂ and
436 CH₄ emissions differed. Most pronounced ~~is~~ was the positive relationship between
437 organic matter content and CO₂ emission (Keller et al., 2020) and the negative
438 relationship between CH₄ and organic matter content reported here. The relationship
439 between organic matter content and CH₄ emission was more complex than the negative
440 GLMM coefficient may suggest, given that high CH₄ emissions were measured along
441 the entire organic matter gradient, particularly at intermediate moisture contents (Figure
442 3). Although not investigated here, the quality of available organic matter may likely be
443 the controlling factor of CH₄ production in our dry inland water sediments (Dalal et al.,
444 2008; Serça et al., 2016; Serrano-Silva et al., 2014; Strom et al., 2003). The quality of
445 organic matter depends on its origin and may be of particular importance in the context

446 of this study regarding the frequency of sediment exposure to the atmosphere. The more
447 frequently a sediment is exposed to the atmosphere, the less labile its organic matter
448 tends to be (Dalal et al., 2008; Serrano-Silva et al., 2014). This might suggest that lower
449 CH₄ production rates can be expected from exposed sediments in aquatic systems that
450 experience frequent water level fluctuations than from those with a generally more
451 constant water level (e.g., reservoirs and lakes, respectively; Table 1). The transition
452 from wet to drying stage triggers microbial processes responsible for organic matter
453 breakdown (Fromin et al., 2010; Jin et al., 2016) that in turn boost CH₄ emissions,
454 mainly in the first hours and/or days after the transition (Jin et al., 2016; Koschorreck,
455 2000; Kosten et al., 2018; Paranaíba et al., 2020). The drying-rewetting history of the
456 sediments in our study may therefore have influenced the observed relationships
457 between bulk organic matter content and CH₄ fluxes.

458 We found a positive effect of moisture on dry inland water CH₄ fluxes (Figure
459 S1; Table 2), which may be related to the fact that the moisture content regulates
460 microbial activity in these water-stressed marginal regions (Baldwin and Mitchell,
461 2000; Manzoni et al., 2012; Sponseller, 2007). CH₄-producing microorganisms thrive in
462 anoxic conditions. Moisture permits anoxic microhabitats and reduces the depth to
463 which oxygen penetrates the sediments. Increased sediment moisture content therefore
464 favors the presence and maintenance of methanogenic (i.e., CH₄-producing) microbial
465 communities and likely reduces CH₄ oxidation, which may help to explain our finding
466 that moisture content and CH₄ emissions were positively correlated (Dalal et al., 2008;
467 Koschorreck, 2000; Serrano-Silva et al., 2014). Ultimately, the positive effect of
468 sediment conductivity and land elevation on dry inland water CH₄ fluxes may be
469 associated with the influence of regional-to-local underlying characteristics that are not
470 explicitly included in our analysis. For example, a water body's trophic status, type of

471 surrounding land cover (e.g., natural vegetation, crops, urbanization), and a sediment's
 472 organic matter quality, microbial community structure and timing and history of its
 473 exposure to the atmosphere may affect CH₄ dynamics (Atekwana et al., 2004; Dalal et
 474 al., 2008; Datry et al., 2018; Lischeid and Kalettka, 2012; Onandia et al., 2021; Serrano-
 475 Silva et al., 2014).

476 **Table 2** | Results from the GLMM describing CH₄ flux from dry inland waters.
 477 Standardized coefficients (β), standard error (SE), *t*-values, 95% confidence intervals
 478 (CI), marginal R squared (R²_m), and conditional R squared (R²_c) are reported. Moisture
 479 and elevation data were transformed by cubic root, organic matter content and
 480 conductivity were log₁₀-transformed, and all predictor variables were z-transformed
 481 before analysis. The colon indicates interaction between the respective variables.

Input variable	CH ₄ flux			
	β	SE	<i>t</i> -value	CI
(Intercept)	3.53	0.30	11.64	2.93 – 4.12
Interaction (Organic matter:Sediment temperature)	0.39	0.10	3.69	0.18 – 0.59
Organic matter	-0.54	0.15	-3.55	-0.85 – -0.24
Moisture	0.49	0.15	3.20	0.19 – 0.79
Conductivity	0.37	0.12	3.01	0.12 – 0.61
Elevation	0.35	0.17	1.98	0.004 – 0.7
Interaction (Moisture:Organic matter)	-0.20	0.10	-2.01	-0.41 – -0.006
R²_m	0.23			
R²_c	0.57			

482

483

484 **Figure 3** | Response of dry inland water CH₄ fluxes (mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹) to the interaction
 485 between organic matter (%), moisture (%) and sediment temperature (°C) (all z-
 486 transformed) arising from the GLMM. Larger circles represent higher CH₄ flux values.

487

488 **3.4 Contribution of CH₄ to the CO₂-equivalent cross-continental inland water fluxes**

489 Summing dry inland water CO₂ fluxes (Keller et al., 2020) with the CH₄ fluxes
 490 presented here (as CO₂-eq; assuming a GWP of 34 for CH₄ compared to CO₂; Myhre et
 491 al., 2013) resulted in a cross-continental mean (± SD) emission rate of 9.6 ± 17.4 g CO₂-
 492 eq m⁻² d⁻¹ (Figure 4), of which ~14% are attributed to CH₄. This estimate represents
 493 about 2.6 ± 4.7 (± SD) g C m⁻² d⁻¹, which is about one order of magnitude higher than
 494 the global organic C burial rate related to lakes, ponds, and reservoirs (~0.1 g C m⁻² d⁻¹;
 495 Mendonça et al., 2017). We found no statistical differences in CH₄ contribution to the
 496 total CO₂-eq emission between types of aquatic systems (mean ± SD; lakes = 9.2 ± 13 g
 497 CO₂-eq m⁻² d⁻¹; ponds = 12.3 ± 11 g CO₂-eq m⁻² d⁻¹; reservoirs = 12.4 ± 29 g CO₂-eq m⁻²
 498 d⁻¹; and streams = 1.1 ± 0.8 g CO₂-eq m⁻² d⁻¹; GLMM, $F = 1.01$, $p = 0.39$ – see Table

499 S7 for pairwise comparisons) (Figure 4). This can likely be explained by the large
500 variability in climate conditions, trophic state, sediment type and water level
501 fluctuations, within and between the different types of systems. Therefore, other factors
502 likely outplay differences arising from the type of aquatic system. As a consequence,
503 the contribution of CH₄ to the total GHG emission estimate did not significantly vary
504 among systems either; it ranged from 10% to 21% contribution to the total CO₂-eq
505 emission from dry inland waters (Figure 4).

506 Upscaling the mean dry inland water CH₄ flux rates from lakes, reservoirs,
507 ponds and streams according to their respective global surface areas revealed that $3.6 \pm$
508 0.4 (\pm standard error of the mean; SEM) Tg CH₄ evade from the dry sediments of inland
509 waters to the atmosphere annually (Table 3). This represents approximately 2.4% (\pm
510 0.2%; SEM) of the global CH₄ emission estimate attributed to water surfaces of lentic
511 and lotic inland water ecosystems ($0.15 \text{ Pg CH}_4 \text{ y}^{-1}$; Rosentreter et al., 2021).
512 Converting our cross-continental CH₄ emission from dry inland waters to C emission
513 indicates that CH₄ adds ~ 2.7 (± 0.3 ; SEM) Tg C y^{-1} (or 0.07%) to the current global C
514 emission estimate from inland waters (3.9 Pg C y^{-1} ; Drake et al., 2018) (Table 3).

515

516 **Figure 4** | Cross-continental mean CO₂-equivalent emission rates (CH₄ – blue; CO₂ –
517 red; g CO₂-eq m⁻² d⁻¹) from dry inland waters (far-right bar) divided by the different
518 types of aquatic systems (lakes, ponds, reservoirs, and streams). CO₂ flux measurements
519 were obtained from Keller et al. (2020) and were associated with the CH₄ flux
520 measurements collected at the same sampling sites. CH₄ fluxes were converted into
521 CO₂-equivalents by multiplying the mass-based CH₄ flux by 34, according to the 100-
522 year GWP (Myhre et al., 2013). Percentage values represent the contribution of each gas
523 to the cross-continental average emission rate in each type of aquatic system. Letter “a”
524 indicates no statistical difference in CH₄ contribution between the types of aquatic
525 systems.

526 **Table 3** | Cross-continental mean fluxes (\pm standard error of the mean; $\text{mg CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$) and cross-continental estimates of dry inland water CH_4
 527 emissions ($\text{Tg CH}_4 \text{ y}^{-1}$, $\text{Pg CO}_2\text{-eq y}^{-1}$, and Tg C y^{-1}) by different types of aquatic systems.

System type	Area of exposed aquatic sediments during one year ^a	CH₄ emission rate	Cross-continental CH₄ emission	Cross-continental CH₄ emission in CO₂ equivalents	Cross-continental CH₄ emission as C emission
	(km²)	(mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹)	(Tg CH₄ y⁻¹)	(Pg CO₂-eq y⁻¹)	(Tg C y⁻¹)
Lakes and reservoirs	187,542 (Marcé et al., 2019)	44 ± 10.9	3.1 ± 0.7	0.1 ± 0.02	2.3 ± 0.5
Ponds	18,390 (Marcé et al., 2019)	38 ± 15.7	0.26 ± 0.1	0.009 ± 0.003	0.2 ± 0.08
Streams and rivers	84,461 (Raymond et al., 2013)	7 ± 5.6	0.21 ± 0.1	0.007 ± 0.006	0.16 ± 0.13
Total	290,393		3.6 ± 0.4	0.11 ± 0.01	2.7 ± 0.3

528 ^a *Seasonal and permanent exposure*

529 4. Conclusions, implications and future perspectives

530 This study provides the first cross-continental assessment of CH₄ fluxes from
531 dry inland waters based on *in situ* measurements. We found that 14% of the cross-
532 continental CO₂-eq emissions from dry inland waters can be attributed to CH₄. Our
533 estimate comes with uncertainties as the number of aquatic systems and climate zones
534 included in this study were non-uniformly represented (i.e., arid and polar regions were
535 not represented at all, and temperate zones were overrepresented), and given the large
536 variation in dry inland water CH₄ fluxes observed within the different types of aquatic
537 systems and climate zones studied here. Moreover, our estimates are solely related to
538 gaseous C species (CH₄ and CO₂) emissions and do not account for nitrous oxide (N₂O)
539 emissions which is an important GHG in these systems as well (Arce et al., 2018). In
540 addition, our global estimate of CH₄ emissions from dry inland waters may be an
541 underestimation because we likely underestimated the global surface area of dry inland
542 waters. While we used a surface area of 290,393 km² for our upscaling exercise, another
543 study that does not differentiate between types of aquatic systems and included
544 wetlands concluded that this area is considerably higher (806,321 km² – Pekel et al.
545 (2016)). Also, during our sampling, we likely generally missed emission peaks (i.e., hot
546 moments of emission) that can occur at the onset of drying (Jin et al., 2016;
547 Koschorreck, 2000; Kosten et al., 2018; Paranaíba et al., 2020). Ultimately, while our
548 estimates account for a good portion of the variability related to weather conditions
549 (since we sampled CH₄ fluxes and environmental parameters across a wide range of
550 locations and climate zones), our estimates do not consider CH₄ fluxes occurring under
551 extreme weather events (e.g., rainy days, snowy days), which therefore represents a
552 knowledge gap in this area of research and certainly deserves further research.

553 While the global CH₄ emission from dry inland waters may be small compared
554 to total aquatic (wet and dry, CO₂ and CH₄) emissions, for individual systems, CH₄
555 emission from dry sediments can be important (Jin et al., 2016). Dry inland-water
556 sediments occupy a temporally varying fraction of aquatic systems due to cycles of
557 rising and falling water levels. Hence, the contribution of dry-sediment CH₄, CO₂ and
558 N₂O emissions to the total emission also varies through time (Almeida et al., 2019; Arce
559 et al., 2018; Keller et al., 2021; Kosten et al., 2018; Paranaíba et al., 2020). The time-
560 integrated contribution of dry sediment to total inland water emissions is likely to
561 increase in the future as drought events are becoming more frequent and more intense.
562 As a result of this and ongoing widespread direct consumptive water uses, large areas of
563 marginal sediments from aquatic systems worldwide will be exposed to the atmosphere
564 (Pekel et al., 2016; Steward et al., 2012; Wurtsbaugh et al., 2017). We argue that future
565 work on aquatic GHG emissions needs to take CH₄, CO₂ and N₂O emissions from these
566 dynamic wet-dry regions into account in order to further improve our estimates of the
567 global GHG budget of inland waters. Such gained insights into the environmental
568 processes that produce and consume GHGs will enable improved predictions of changes
569 in atmospheric GHG concentrations under varying climate change scenarios.

570

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597

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600 **7. References**

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Highlights should be submitted in a separate editable file in the online submission system. Please use 'Highlights' in the file name and include 3 to 5 bullet points (maximum 85 characters, including spaces, per bullet point).

- Dry inland waters are hotspots of C emission to the atmosphere
- CH₄ contributed 10 – 21% to total C emissions (in CO₂-eq) of dry inland waters
- The contribution of CH₄ (total C emissions) did not differ between types of systems
- Globally, dry inland waters emit 2.7 Tg C-CH₄ y⁻¹ and emissions are likely rising
- More CH₄ emission data are needed to improve the global GHG budget of inland waters

1 **Cross-continental importance of CH₄ emissions from dry inland-**
 2 **waters**

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64 **Graphical abstract**

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79 **Abstract**

80 Despite substantial advances in quantifying greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from dry
81 inland waters, existing estimates mainly consist of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions.
82 However, methane (CH₄) may also be relevant due to its higher Global Warming
83 Potential (GWP). We report CH₄ emissions from dry inland water sediments to i)
84 provide a cross-continental estimate of such emissions for different types of aquatic
85 systems (i.e., lakes, ponds, reservoirs, and streams) and climate zones (i.e., tropical,
86 continental, and temperate); and ii) determine the environmental factors that control
87 these emissions. CH₄ emissions from dry inland waters were consistently higher than
88 emissions observed in adjacent uphill soils, across climate zones and in all aquatic
89 systems except for streams. However, the CH₄ contribution (normalized to CO₂
90 equivalents; CO₂-eq) to the total GHG emissions of dry inland waters was similar for all
91 types of aquatic systems and varied from 10 – 21%. Although we discuss multiple
92 controlling factors, dry inland water CH₄ emissions were most strongly related to
93 sediment organic matter content and moisture. Summing CO₂ and CH₄ emissions
94 revealed a cross-continental average emission of $9.6 \pm 17.4 \text{ g CO}_2\text{-eq m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ from dry
95 inland waters. We argue that increasing droughts likely expand the worldwide surface
96 area of atmosphere-exposed aquatic sediments, thereby increasing global dry inland
97 water CH₄ emissions. Hence, CH₄ cannot be ignored if we want to fully understand the
98 carbon (C) cycle of dry sediments.

99 **Keywords:** Methane; Dry sediments; Aquatic ecosystems; Greenhouse gases;

100

101

102 **1. Introduction**

103 Inland waters (e.g., lakes, ponds, reservoirs, rivers) are complex ecosystems that
104 process large amounts of allochthonous and autochthonous organic matter (Attermeyer
105 et al., 2017; Clair and Ehrman, 1996; Friedl and Wüest, 2002; Van Cappellen and
106 Maavara, 2016) and play important roles as sources and sinks within the global C cycle
107 (Cole et al., 2007; Rosentreter et al., 2021; Tranvik et al., 2009). In aquatic ecosystems,
108 organic matter undergoes various biogeochemical processes, including its
109 decomposition into gaseous carbon (C) species (Mattson and Likens, 1992) such as
110 carbon dioxide (CO₂) and methane (CH₄) (Bastviken et al., 2011; DelSontro et al.,
111 2018; Raymond et al., 2013). In addition, part of the organic matter can settle and
112 accumulate in sediments (Heathcote et al., 2015; Mendonça et al., 2017). According to
113 C-budget studies, approximately 0.06 – 0.25 Pg C y⁻¹ are estimated to be buried in
114 sediments of inland waters worldwide (Anderson et al., 2020; Mendonça et al., 2017),
115 whereas approximately 3.9 Pg C y⁻¹ are emitted from inland waters to the atmosphere as
116 CO₂ and as CH₄ (Drake et al., 2018).

117 After CO₂, CH₄ is the most important gas contributing to the global greenhouse
118 effect. Considering the Global Warming Potential (GWP) over a 100-year time horizon,
119 one gram of CH₄ exerts an atmospheric heating power equivalent to 34 grams of CO₂
120 (Myhre et al., 2013). Globally, approximately 0.15 Pg of C are annually emitted from
121 freshwaters to the atmosphere as CH₄ (not considering wetlands, rice paddies and
122 aquaculture ponds). About 0.13 Pg C y⁻¹ of these emissions evade to the atmosphere
123 from lentic (non-flowing) aquatic systems such as lakes, ponds and reservoirs, and
124 ~0.02 Pg C y⁻¹ from lotic (flowing) systems such as streams and rivers (Rosentreter et
125 al., 2021). A large part of the CH₄ production in aquatic systems occurs in anoxic
126 sediments via microbial degradation of organic matter (Bastviken et al., 2004). The

127 resulting CH₄ that escapes microbial oxidation at the sediment-water interface and water
128 column (Granéli et al., 1996; Heilman and Carlton, 2001) reaches the atmosphere
129 through diffusion (Bastviken et al., 2004; Cole and Caraco, 1998), ebullition (bubbling)
130 (Bastviken et al., 2004), plant-mediated transport (Abril et al., 2005), and by the passage
131 of deep, CH₄-rich waters through the turbines of hydroelectric reservoirs (“degassing”)
132 (Abril et al., 2005; Kemenes et al., 2016). In addition, even after exposure to
133 atmospheric air, sediment CH₄ production can continue in anoxic microhabitats (Dalal
134 et al., 2008; Serrano-Silva et al., 2014). However, a large share of the CH₄ produced in
135 these micro-regions is oxidized to CO₂ by methanotrophic bacteria before evasion to the
136 atmosphere, especially during the first hours or days after atmospheric exposure
137 (Koschorreck, 2000). The remaining CH₄ may directly diffuse to the atmosphere.

138 Many inland water ecosystems worldwide experience periods of drying (Marcé
139 et al., 2019; Messenger et al., 2021). Drying can result from natural (i.e., intermittency of
140 rivers and ponds) or human-induced (i.e., human actions in reservoirs and lakes) water
141 level and flow fluctuations (Beaulieu et al., 2018; Di Baldassarre et al., 2018; Leigh et
142 al., 2016; Wurtsbaugh et al., 2017). During the dry season, considerable areas of
143 marginal aquatic sediments are exposed directly to the atmosphere. Pekel et al. (2016)
144 estimated that ~800,000 km² (or 18%) of the global surface area that is covered by
145 inland waters are subject to seasonal atmospheric exposure, especially non-flowing
146 reaches, which dominate the hydrological networks (Messenger et al., 2021). Moreover,
147 15% of the global reservoir surfaces are dry (Keller et al., 2021).

148 Exposed aquatic sediments may represent a substantial source of GHG to the
149 atmosphere (Keller et al., 2020; Marcé et al., 2019; von Schiller et al., 2014) but are
150 seldom considered in global C emission estimates. Local, regional, and global GHG
151 emission estimates from dry inland waters have emerged and improved considerably in

152 the last decade (Beaulieu et al., 2018; Gallo et al., 2014; Harrison et al., 2017; Jin et al.,
153 2016; Marcé et al., 2019), especially for CO₂ (Almeida et al., 2019; Catalán et al., 2014;
154 Deshmukh et al., 2018; Keller et al., 2020; Obrador et al., 2018; von Schiller et al.,
155 2014). Keller et al. (2020) found that 0.12 ± 0.13 Pg C y⁻¹ are added to recent global
156 inland water C emission estimates when CO₂ emissions from dry inland waters are
157 considered. However, compared to CO₂, other GHGs have been poorly assessed in
158 drying sediments, preventing a complete picture of their role in biogeochemical cycling.
159 Particularly for CH₄, the number of studies on dry inland waters is not sufficient to
160 reliably upscale CH₄ fluxes of these habitats to the global scale (Marcé et al., 2019).
161 Because of this, a recent global estimate of GHG emissions from dry reservoir
162 sediments assumed zero CH₄ emissions (Keller et al., 2021). In addition, the
163 environmental drivers regulating CH₄ fluxes from dry inland waters are not fully
164 understood. Therefore, the contribution of CH₄ emission from exposed sediments to
165 global C emission from inland waters remains to be quantified.

166 This study aims to assess the importance of CH₄ fluxes from the exposed
167 sediments of different types of aquatic systems (i.e., lakes, ponds, reservoirs, and
168 streams) located in various climate zones across the globe. To achieve this, dry inland
169 water CH₄ fluxes were i) compared to CH₄ fluxes observed in adjacent uphill (natural
170 terrestrial) soils; ii) compared to the CO₂ fluxes obtained at the same locations where
171 CH₄ fluxes were measured; iii) related to physical and chemical sediment properties that
172 were concurrently measured along with CH₄ in order to identify drivers of CH₄ fluxes
173 from exposed sediments; iv) scaled up to the respective dry global surface areas
174 associated with each type of aquatic system studied here, to v) ultimately determine
175 whether dry inland water CH₄ fluxes represent a significant share of the global C
176 emission estimates from inland waters. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first

177 cross-continental study quantifying the magnitude and environmental controls of CH₄
178 fluxes from the dry sediments of multiple aquatic system types.

179

180 2. Methods

181 2.1 Studied sites and sampling strategy

182 This study includes measurements in 89 hydrologically independent aquatic
183 systems (lakes, $n = 45$; ponds, $n = 16$; reservoirs, $n = 19$; and streams, $n = 9$), located in
184 three of the five global climate zones (tropical, $n = 24$; continental, $n = 11$; and
185 temperate, $n = 54$) (Kottek et al., 2006) (Figure 1), which were conducted by 22
186 research groups from 10 countries. The research groups were classified as levels of a
187 variable named “*research group*”, which were used in the analysis of CH₄ flux drivers
188 (see below). The 89 systems are a subset of the 196 aquatic systems included in a recent
189 global study on CO₂ emission from exposed sediments by Keller et al. (2020). The
190 subset was created based on the availability of CH₄ flux data (i.e., not all datasets
191 contained CH₄ data).

192 At each sampling site, two distinct regions were sampled: i) exposed sediment –
193 hereafter named as “*dry inland water*”, which corresponds to an area with air-exposed
194 sediment that experiences periodic and/or recent historical inundation (Marcé et al.,
195 2019); and ii) adjacent uphill soil, which corresponds to the adjacent terrestrial region
196 that is not inundated. At each region, measurements were performed in triplicates that
197 were, if possible, conducted at least 1 meter apart from each other to capture spatial
198 within-region variability.

199

200 **Figure 1** | Cross-continental distribution of the sampling sites (white dots) across the
 201 different climate zones according to the Köppen-Geiger climate classification system
 202 (Kottek et al., 2006).

203

204 **2.2 CH₄ flux measurements**

205 Between 2016 and 2017, *in situ* measurements of CH₄ flux (mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹)
 206 were conducted using opaque chambers connected to infrared gas analyzers in closed
 207 gas loops. The chambers were gently placed over the sediment/soil surface to avoid
 208 disturbance and gas leakage during the measurements, and where necessary, sealed with
 209 clay (Lesmeister and Koschorreck, 2017). Changes in CH₄ partial pressure (*m*CH₄) were

210 monitored within the chambers over 3-5 minutes, and the fluxes were calculated
211 following:

$$212 \quad FCH_4 = \left(\frac{dmCH_4}{dt} \right) \times \left(\frac{V}{RTA} \right) \quad (1)$$

213 where $dmCH_4$ is the slope of change in mCH_4 (ppm) over time (dt , given in seconds), V
214 is the volume of the chamber (m^3), R is the gas constant = $8.205746 \times 10^{-5} m^3 atm mol^{-1}$
215 K^{-1} , T is the air temperature (K), and A is the surface area covered by the chamber (m^2).

216 Dry inland waters lack CH_4 ebullition as an emission route (Marcé et al., 2019),
217 mainly due to the absence of water overlying the sediments. Therefore, our
218 measurements represent only the diffusion of CH_4 at the sediment/soil-atmosphere
219 interface. Opaque chambers were used in order to minimize temperature changes during
220 measurements, which may affect the gas exchange at the interface between
221 sediment/soil and headspace (Welles et al., 2001). Chamber deployments were
222 performed on top of bare sediment/soil, avoiding vegetated surfaces.

223

224 **2.3 Sediment/soil characterization**

225 After the flux measurements, surface sediment/soil samples were collected from
226 the plot of the flux measurement, placed in plastic bags and stored in thermal cooler
227 boxes for subsequent laboratory analysis. Air and sediment/soil temperature ($^{\circ}C$) were
228 measured *in situ*, and elevation (m.a.s.l., meters above sea level) was either measured *in*
229 *situ* or read from a map. Sediment/soil texture was determined following a manipulative
230 test developed by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO,
231 2020) and distinguished as clay, light clay, heavy loam, sandy loam, loamy sand, and
232 sand. 10 g of fresh sediment/soil were mixed in 25 mL distilled water for the

233 determination of electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$) and pH by measuring the suspended
234 solution (after 1 h standing) with conventional electrodes (Keller et al., 2020). Moisture
235 content (% weight loss) was determined by drying 5 g of fresh sediment/soil at 105 °C
236 until reaching a constant weight (Keller et al., 2020). Afterward, the samples were
237 combusted at 500 °C until constant weight for the determination of the organic matter
238 content (% weight loss) (Dean, 1974).

239

240 ***2.4 Data analysis and statistical procedures***

241 Each sampling site was assigned to a climate zone according to “The World
242 Maps of Köppen-Geiger Climate Classification” (Kottek et al., 2006). For each
243 sampling site, we then calculated the contribution of dry inland water CH₄ emission to
244 the total (i.e., CO₂ + CH₄) GHG emission in CO₂-equivalents (CO₂-eq; see below how
245 CH₄ was converted to CO₂-eq) for each type of aquatic system (lakes, ponds, reservoirs,
246 and streams). The CO₂ flux data was retrieved from Keller et al. (2020), and each CO₂
247 flux measurement was associated with the CH₄ flux measurement collected at the same
248 sampling site. For all analyses, triplicate measurements were averaged, and one average
249 value per parameter at each sampling site was used.

250 To test the relationships between environmental variables and dry inland water
251 CH₄ fluxes, a generalized linear mixed model (GLMM) was performed using the
252 “*glmer*” function in the “*lme4*” package (Bates et al., 2015) in R (v. 4.0.2) (R Core
253 Team, 2018). We used sediment texture, sediment temperature, pH, electrical
254 conductivity, moisture and organic matter content, as well as latitude, elevation, annual
255 mean precipitation, and annual mean air temperature as fixed effects. Given that CH₄
256 fluxes are primarily driven by the availability and quality of organic matter, moisture,

257 and temperature (Aben et al., 2017; Grasset et al., 2018; Koschorreck, 2000; Sobek et
258 al., 2012; Yvon-Durocher et al., 2014), the interactions between i) organic matter
259 content and temperature, ii) organic matter and moisture content, and iii) moisture
260 content and temperature of the sediments were also included as fixed effects. The
261 variables research group, type of aquatic system, and climate zone were used as crossed
262 random factors to account for the dependencies in the data. We used GLMM because
263 preliminary analyses showed that the distribution of the residuals of the linear mixed
264 models followed a logarithmic distribution and, therefore, the Gamma family (*link=log*)
265 was applied in the GLMM (Lo and Andrews, 2015). A value of $13 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ was
266 added to the CH_4 flux data (i.e., $x + 13$) to avoid negative values which would hamper
267 our GLMM analysis since the Gamma family (*link=log*) does not allow negative values
268 in the response variable. The observed negative CH_4 flux values (i.e., influx; see section
269 3. Results and Discussion) were very small in magnitude compared with emissions –
270 most of the influx data were close to zero and the strongest influx was roughly 7 mg
271 $\text{CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$, whereas the efflux rates were often two orders of magnitude greater than
272 influx rates. Therefore, the addition of the fixed value aforementioned does not have a
273 relevant impact on the overall driver analysis. Logarithmic and cubic root
274 transformations were adopted for electrical conductivity and organic matter content ($x +$
275 1), moisture, and elevation, respectively, to meet the conditions of normality and
276 homoscedasticity of variances. Before analysis, collinearity between predictor variables
277 was assessed using the variance inflation factor (VIF) function in the “*usdm*” package
278 (Naimi et al., 2014) in R. Variables with VIF values > 5 (which is indicative of
279 collinearity) were excluded from the procedures (Akinwande et al., 2015). In the
280 GLMM presented here, the excluded variable was annual precipitation. The model was
281 simplified by removing non-significant predictors. GLMMs were also used to assess

282 differences in CH₄ fluxes, moisture, and organic matter content among aquatic system
283 types (fixed factor), between sampling regions (fixed factor), and between climate zones
284 (fixed factor), with the variable research group defined as a crossed random factor.
285 Type-III ANOVAs were used to test the significance of the fixed factors, with degrees
286 of freedom and *p* values calculated using the Kenward-Roger approximation (Kenward
287 and Roger, 1997) through the “*lmerTest*” and “*pbkrtest*” packages (Halekoh and
288 Højsgaard, 2014; Kuznetsova et al., 2017). Least-square means (classical Yates
289 contrasts), as well as pairwise differences, were computed by the “*ls_means*” function
290 (“*lmerTest*” package). For all statistical procedures, a *p* value < 0.05 was adopted as the
291 threshold level of statistical significance.

292 Finally, to obtain an estimate of cross-continental CH₄ emission from dry inland
293 waters, we multiplied the average CH₄ flux rate of each type of aquatic system by its
294 respective global associated desiccated surface area (for lakes, reservoirs, and ponds:
295 Marcé et al., 2019; for streams: Raymond et al., 2013), and then summed them up. Also,
296 cross-continental CH₄ emissions from dry inland waters were converted into CO₂-eq
297 emissions by using the 100-year time horizon GWP factor of 34 (Myhre et al., 2013).

298

299 **3. Results and Discussion**

300 ***3.1 Contrasting CH₄ fluxes from dry inland waters and surrounding terrestrial areas***

301 CH₄ fluxes from dry sediments of inland waters and adjacent uphill (terrestrial)
302 soils ranged from -8 to 352 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹, with a median of 0.08 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹ and
303 an interquartile range (IQR) of 4.1 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹ (mean ± standard deviation (SD): 20
304 ± 60 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹) (Figure 2). CH₄ uptake was found in 51 uphill soil regions (57%)
305 and 21 dry inland water regions (23%) (Figure 2D – see Figure 2E and F for system

306 type and climate zones). Variability of CH₄ fluxes was larger among dry inland water
307 sediments than among uphill soils (Figure 2A). Uphill sites tend to be drained/dry and
308 oxic, which represents unfavorable conditions for CH₄ production but favorable
309 conditions for CH₄ consumption (von Fischer and Hedin, 2007). On the other hand,
310 exposed inland-water sediments may sometimes be fully desiccated, showing little or no
311 CH₄ production, or waterlogged with potential anoxia supporting CH₄ production and
312 emission (Koschorreck, 2000). While CO₂ emissions from dry inland waters tend to be
313 lower than those from uphill soils (Almeida et al., 2019; Catalán et al., 2014; Jin et al.,
314 2016; Keller et al., 2020; von Schiller et al., 2014), the pattern we observed for CH₄ was
315 opposite. Average CH₄ emissions from dry inland waters were significantly higher than
316 those from adjacent uphill soils (Figure 2A; Table 1) (mean ± SD and median – IQR,
317 respectively; dry inland water: 40 ± 80 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹, and 1 – 28.4 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹;
318 uphill soil: 1 ± 4 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹, and -0.07 – 1.1 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹; GLMM: $t = -9.61$, $p <$
319 0.001). The difference in CH₄ emissions from the two different regions may be
320 attributed to differences in moisture content as well as quality and quantity of organic
321 matter (Dalal et al., 2008; Serça et al., 2016; Serrano-Silva et al., 2014). When air-
322 exposed sediments are still wet, anoxia generally prevails below the upper few
323 millimeters of the sediment (Koschorreck and Darwich, 2003), thereby sustaining CH₄
324 production. When sediments start to dry out, CH₄ production through organic matter
325 decomposition can still take place in anoxic microhabitats (Dalal et al., 2008;
326 Koschorreck, 2000; Serrano-Silva et al., 2014). As exposed sediments of inland waters
327 dry out further, newly formed fractures ease the contact of deeper sediment layers with
328 atmospheric oxygen (Fromin et al., 2010; Kosten et al., 2018; Paranaíba et al., 2020).
329 The expansion of the oxic layer in the sediment provokes changes in microbial
330 communities and their activity (Borken and Matzner, 2009; Jin et al., 2016; Rodrigo et

331 al., 1997), favoring aerobic metabolisms (e.g., CH₄ oxidation; Jäckel et al., 2001;
332 Koschorreck, 2000), and eventually leading to a reduction in CH₄ emissions (Kosten et
333 al., 2018; Paranaíba et al., 2020). Furthermore, the microbial community in water-
334 stressed sediments is expected to desiccate (Borken and Matzner, 2009; Jin et al., 2016;
335 Rodrigo et al., 1997), which can be expected to diminish the potential of CH₄
336 production likely contributing to the wide range in CH₄ fluxes from dry inland-water
337 sediments. The importance of moisture content in regulating CH₄ emission is further
338 exemplified by the mean moisture content being consistently higher in dry inland-water
339 sediments than in uphill soils across all systems globally (mean ± SD; dry inland water:
340 33.1 ± 21.4%, uphill soil: 17 ± 9.4%; GLMM: $t = -7.03$, $p < 0.001$), corresponding with
341 the generally higher CH₄ emissions from the dry inland-water sediments. Mean organic
342 matter content, however, was similar for the two regions (mean ± SD; dry inland water:
343 7.9 ± 7%, uphill soil: 8.2 ± 7.5%; GLMM: $t = 0.19$, $p = 0.84$).

344

345 ***3.2 Dry inland waters CH₄ flux variability across aquatic systems and climate zones***

346 No statistical differences in CH₄ fluxes were found between the different types
347 of dry inland water systems (GLMM, $F = 0.63$, $p = 0.59$ – see Table S1 for pairwise
348 comparisons), due to the relatively high variability among sites within each type (Figure
349 2B; Table 1). Dry inland water sediments were a source of CH₄ in almost all cases,
350 while adjacent uphill soils could be either a source or a sink of CH₄, depending on the
351 site (Figure 2E). Dry inland water CH₄ fluxes were, on average (± SD), 48 ± 91 mg CH₄
352 m⁻² d⁻¹ ($n = 45$; median – IQR: 2.3 – 48.2 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹) in lakes, 38 ± 63 mg CH₄ m⁻²
353 d⁻¹ ($n = 16$; median – IQR: 0.7 – 84 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹) in ponds, 36 ± 78 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹
354 ($n = 19$; median – IQR: 0.08 – 13.9 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹) in reservoirs, and 7 ± 17 mg CH₄
355 m⁻² d⁻¹ ($n = 9$; median – IQR: 0.1 – 3.5 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹) in streams (Figure 2B; Table 1).

356 The lower CH₄ flux rate from dry streams corresponded with their significantly lower
357 mean (\pm SD) moisture and organic matter content when compared to lakes, ponds and
358 reservoirs (moisture content: streams: $20 \pm 27\%$, lakes: $31 \pm 20\%$, ponds: $52 \pm 21\%$,
359 reservoirs: $27 \pm 10\%$; GLMM, $F = 6.25$, $p = 0.0006$ – see Table S2 for pairwise
360 comparisons; organic matter content: streams: $1 \pm 1\%$, lakes: $9 \pm 8\%$, ponds: $8 \pm 4\%$,
361 reservoirs: $9 \pm 6\%$; GLMM, $F = 3.48$, $p = 0.01$ – see Table S3 for pairwise
362 comparisons). In fact, dry sediments of rivers and streams tend to have less organic
363 matter content than dry sediments of lentic water bodies (Gómez-gener et al., 2015).
364 Rivers and streams are more sensitive to variations in hydrological cycles (i.e., are
365 subject to high and recurrent water stress). In addition, water flow erodes fine-grained
366 sediment, which hinders organic matter accumulation at the margins of these systems
367 (Boix-Fayos et al., 2015; Gómez-Gener et al., 2016).

368 The CH₄ fluxes presented here were higher than values reported for individual
369 dry inland water CH₄-emission in earlier studies conducted in different aquatic systems
370 (Table 1). We can only speculate about the underlying reason, which may be related to
371 drier conditions or low (quality) organic matter content found in the systems from
372 earlier studies. For instance, the mean \pm SD of organic matter content found in 16
373 ephemeral streams by Gallo et al. (2014) was $3 \pm 2.7\%$, and mean \pm SD dry CH₄
374 emission was 0.4 ± 0.5 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹, which is both considerably lower than the
375 values we found.

376 The CH₄ fluxes per square meter from dry inland waters were lower than those
377 from surface waters reported in the literature (Table 1). This may be related to lower
378 oxygen availability in submerged sediments possibly leading to higher CH₄ production
379 and lower CH₄ consumption. In addition, the littoral regions of streams and reservoirs
380 tend to be depleted in labile organic matter due to frequent water level changes, which

381 hampers the production of CH₄ in these regions (Dalal et al., 2008; Serrano-Silva et al.,
382 2014).

383 No statistical differences in dry inland water CH₄ fluxes were found between
384 climate zones (GLMM, $F = 1.41$, $p = 0.22$ – see Table S4 for pairwise comparisons),
385 again likely due to the substantial variation in fluxes within climate zones. CH₄ efflux
386 prevailed in dry inland-water sediments across climate zones, while CH₄ influx was
387 more evident in adjacent uphill soils (except for soils from tropical zones) (Figure 2F).
388 Mean (\pm SD) dry inland water CH₄ fluxes were 96 ± 128 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹ ($n = 11$;
389 median – IQR: $0.5 - 232.1$ mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹) in continental zones, 54 ± 77 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹,
390 ¹ ($n = 24$; median – IQR: $0.08 - 87.5$ mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹) in tropical zones, and 22 ± 58 mg
391 CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹ ($n = 54$; median – IQR: $-0.03 - 3.7$ mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹) in temperate zones
392 (Figure 2C). Interestingly, the highest emissions obtained in our study were observed at
393 sampling sites located in the continental zone (mean \pm SD: 352 ± 150 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹;
394 293 ± 351 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹; and 232 ± 201 mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹), which ended up determining
395 the higher mean CH₄ emission attributed to continental zones. In addition, local
396 characteristics not captured in our sampling design (e.g., surrounding land use, trophic
397 state, microbial community structure, timing of atmospheric exposure) rather than
398 regional characteristics (e.g., mean annual temperature) may be responsible for both the
399 high CH₄ emission rates and the high variability observed in our measurements. Mean
400 sediment moisture content was similar among climate zones (GLMM, $F = 2.50$, $p =$
401 0.09 ; see Table S5 for pairwise comparisons). The mean moisture content (\pm SD) in dry
402 sediments was $37 \pm 22\%$ in temperate zones, $32 \pm 27\%$ in continental zones, and $25 \pm$
403 14% in tropical zones. The highest mean (\pm SD) organic matter content was observed in
404 dry sediments of tropical zones ($11 \pm 9\%$), followed by those in temperate ($7 \pm 5\%$) and

405 continental zones ($4 \pm 5\%$) (GLMM, $F = 5.37$, $p = 0.006$ – see Table S6 for pairwise
 406 comparisons).

407

408

409 **Figure 2** | Boxplot of CH_4 fluxes ($\text{mg CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$) from dry inland waters (red boxes)
 410 and adjacent uphill soils (cyan boxes) (A); in different types of aquatic systems (B); and
 411 different climate zones (C). Number of cases of CH_4 influx (yellow bars) and efflux
 412 (blue bars) from dry inland waters (DIW) and adjacent uphill soils (UPS) (D); in
 413 different types of aquatic systems (E); and different climate zones (F). In A, B and C,

414 the y-axes are presented as logarithmic scale (\log_{10}), the lines within the boxes indicate
 415 the median, the boxes delimit the 25th and 75th percentiles, and the whiskers delimit the
 416 5th and 95th percentiles.

417 **Table 1 | Upper part:** Mean \pm standard deviation of CH₄ fluxes (mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹) from
 418 dry inland waters (dry sediments) and adjacent uphill soils among lakes, ponds,
 419 reservoirs, and streams. **Middle part:** Mean \pm standard deviation of CH₄ fluxes (mg
 420 CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹) from other dry inland waters (documented in the literature). **Bottom part:**
 421 Global mean \pm standard deviation of CH₄ fluxes (mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹) from surface waters
 422 of lakes, ponds, reservoirs, and streams (documented in the literature).

System type	CH₄ flux (mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹)	Reference
Lakes (n = 45)		
<i>Dry sediment</i>	48 \pm 91	
<i>Uphill soil</i>	1 \pm 5	
Ponds (n = 16)		
<i>Dry sediment</i>	38 \pm 63	
<i>Uphill soil</i>	0.3 \pm 1	
Reservoirs (n = 19)		
<i>Dry sediment</i>	36 \pm 78	This study
<i>Uphill soil</i>	2 \pm 4	
Streams (n = 9)		
<i>Dry sediment</i>	7 \pm 17	
<i>Uphill soil</i>	0.2 \pm 0.7	
All systems (n = 89)		
<i>Dry sediment</i>	40 \pm 80	
<i>Uphill soil</i>	1 \pm 4	
Lake (Brazil)	1.4 \pm 0.15 (Amazonian floodplain)	Koschorreck, 2000
Ponds (Spain)	4.8 \pm 3.8 (Dry bed)	Obrador et al. 2018
Reservoir (Brazil)	0.9 \pm 6.9 (Drawdown)	Amorim et al. 2019
Reservoir (China)	7 \pm 8.9 (Drawdown)	Chen et al. 2011
Reservoir (China)	4 \pm 1.5 (Drawdown)	Yang et al. 2012
Reservoir (China)	7.7 \pm 5 (Drawdown)	Hao et al. 2019
Reservoir (Laos)	27 \pm 36 (Drawdown)	Serça et al. 2016
Reservoir (Germany)	4.1 ^a (Drawdown)	Marcé et al. 2019
Reservoir (Germany)	7.2 ^a (Drawdown)	Marcé et al. 2019
Reservoir (Spain)	0 (Drawdown)	Marcé et al. 2019
Reservoir (Spain)	4.1 ^a (Drawdown)	Marcé et al. 2019
Reservoir (Spain)	0.3 ^a (Drawdown)	Marcé et al. 2019
Streams (United States)	0.4 \pm 0.5 (Dry river bed)	Gallo et al. 2014
Streams (Spain)	3.2 \pm 0.9 (Dry river and impoundment beds)	Gómez-Gener et al. 2015
Global CH₄ flux rates from surface waters (mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹)		

Lakes	153 ± 293	Rosentreter et al. 2021
Ponds	12 ± 30	Holgerson and Raymond 2016
Reservoirs	165 ± 369	Rosentreter et al. 2021
Streams	112 ± 425	Rosentreter et al. 2021

^a Mean values

423 3.3 Drivers of CH₄ fluxes

424 The fixed effects resulting from the GLMM modeling on dry inland water CH₄
425 fluxes explained 23% of the total variance (marginal R squared, R²m), and fixed and
426 random effects together explained 57% of the total variance (conditional R squared,
427 R²c) (Table 2). Organic matter content and the interaction between organic matter
428 content and sediment temperature were the strongest predictors of CH₄ fluxes from dry
429 inland waters ($p < 0.001$; Figure S1; Table 2), followed by moisture, conductivity ($p <$
430 0.01 ; Figure S1; Table 2), elevation and the interaction between moisture and organic
431 matter content ($p < 0.05$; Figure S1; Table 2). This suggests that local sediment
432 characteristics rather than regional characteristics such as annual mean temperature
433 drive CH₄ emissions, which agrees with findings for dry inland-water CO₂ emissions
434 (Keller et al., 2020) (Figure S1; Table 2). However, the particular drivers of CO₂ and
435 CH₄ emissions differed. Most pronounced was the positive relationship between organic
436 matter content and CO₂ emission (Keller et al., 2020) and the negative relationship
437 between CH₄ and organic matter content reported here. The relationship between
438 organic matter content and CH₄ emission was more complex than the negative GLMM
439 coefficient may suggest, given that high CH₄ emissions were measured along the entire
440 organic matter gradient, particularly at intermediate moisture contents (Figure 3).
441 Although not investigated here, the quality of available organic matter may likely be the
442 controlling factor of CH₄ production in our dry inland water sediments (Dalal et al.,
443 2008; Serça et al., 2016; Serrano-Silva et al., 2014; Strom et al., 2003). The quality of
444 organic matter depends on its origin and may be of particular importance in the context

445 of this study regarding the frequency of sediment exposure to the atmosphere. The more
446 frequently a sediment is exposed to the atmosphere, the less labile its organic matter
447 tends to be (Dalal et al., 2008; Serrano-Silva et al., 2014). This might suggest that lower
448 CH₄ production rates can be expected from exposed sediments in aquatic systems that
449 experience frequent water level fluctuations than from those with a generally more
450 constant water level (e.g., reservoirs and lakes, respectively; Table 1). The transition
451 from wet to drying stage triggers microbial processes responsible for organic matter
452 breakdown (Fromin et al., 2010; Jin et al., 2016) that in turn boost CH₄ emissions,
453 mainly in the first hours and/or days after the transition (Jin et al., 2016; Koschorreck,
454 2000; Kosten et al., 2018; Paranaíba et al., 2020). The drying-rewetting history of the
455 sediments in our study may therefore have influenced the observed relationships
456 between bulk organic matter content and CH₄ fluxes.

457 We found a positive effect of moisture on dry inland water CH₄ fluxes (Figure
458 S1; Table 2), which may be related to the fact that the moisture content regulates
459 microbial activity in these water-stressed marginal regions (Baldwin and Mitchell,
460 2000; Manzoni et al., 2012; Sponseller, 2007). CH₄-producing microorganisms thrive in
461 anoxic conditions. Moisture permits anoxic microhabitats and reduces the depth to
462 which oxygen penetrates the sediments. Increased sediment moisture content therefore
463 favors the presence and maintenance of methanogenic (i.e., CH₄-producing) microbial
464 communities and likely reduces CH₄ oxidation, which may help to explain our finding
465 that moisture content and CH₄ emissions were positively correlated (Dalal et al., 2008;
466 Koschorreck, 2000; Serrano-Silva et al., 2014). Ultimately, the positive effect of
467 sediment conductivity and land elevation on dry inland water CH₄ fluxes may be
468 associated with the influence of regional-to-local underlying characteristics that are not
469 explicitly included in our analysis. For example, a water body's trophic status, type of

470 surrounding land cover (e.g., natural vegetation, crops, urbanization), and a sediment's
 471 organic matter quality, microbial community structure and timing and history of its
 472 exposure to the atmosphere may affect CH₄ dynamics (Atekwana et al., 2004; Dalal et
 473 al., 2008; Datry et al., 2018; Lischeid and Kalettka, 2012; Onandia et al., 2021; Serrano-
 474 Silva et al., 2014).

475 **Table 2** | Results from the GLMM describing CH₄ flux from dry inland waters.
 476 Standardized coefficients (β), standard error (SE), *t*-values, 95% confidence intervals
 477 (CI), marginal R squared (R²_m), and conditional R squared (R²_c) are reported. Moisture
 478 and elevation data were transformed by cubic root, organic matter content and
 479 conductivity were log₁₀-transformed, and all predictor variables were z-transformed
 480 before analysis. The colon indicates interaction between the respective variables.

Input variable	CH ₄ flux			
	β	SE	<i>t</i> -value	CI
(Intercept)	3.53	0.30	11.64	2.93 – 4.12
Interaction (Organic matter:Sediment temperature)	0.39	0.10	3.69	0.18 – 0.59
Organic matter	-0.54	0.15	-3.55	-0.85 – -0.24
Moisture	0.49	0.15	3.20	0.19 – 0.79
Conductivity	0.37	0.12	3.01	0.12 – 0.61
Elevation	0.35	0.17	1.98	0.004 – 0.7
Interaction (Moisture:Organic matter)	-0.20	0.10	-2.01	-0.41 – -0.006
R²_m	0.23			
R²_c	0.57			

481

482

483 **Figure 3** | Response of dry inland water CH₄ fluxes (mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹) to the interaction
 484 between organic matter (%), moisture (%) and sediment temperature (°C) (all z-
 485 transformed) arising from the GLMM. Larger circles represent higher CH₄ flux values.

486

487 **3.4 Contribution of CH₄ to the CO₂-equivalent cross-continental inland water fluxes**

488 Summing dry inland water CO₂ fluxes (Keller et al., 2020) with the CH₄ fluxes
 489 presented here (as CO₂-eq; assuming a GWP of 34 for CH₄ compared to CO₂; Myhre et
 490 al., 2013) resulted in a cross-continental mean (± SD) emission rate of 9.6 ± 17.4 g CO₂-
 491 eq m⁻² d⁻¹ (Figure 4), of which ~14% are attributed to CH₄. This estimate represents
 492 about 2.6 ± 4.7 (± SD) g C m⁻² d⁻¹, which is about one order of magnitude higher than
 493 the global organic C burial rate related to lakes, ponds, and reservoirs (~0.1 g C m⁻² d⁻¹;
 494 Mendonça et al., 2017). We found no statistical differences in CH₄ contribution to the
 495 total CO₂-eq emission between types of aquatic systems (mean ± SD; lakes = 9.2 ± 13 g
 496 CO₂-eq m⁻² d⁻¹; ponds = 12.3 ± 11 g CO₂-eq m⁻² d⁻¹; reservoirs = 12.4 ± 29 g CO₂-eq m⁻²
 497 d⁻¹; and streams = 1.1 ± 0.8 g CO₂-eq m⁻² d⁻¹; GLMM, $F = 1.01$, $p = 0.39$ – see Table

498 S7 for pairwise comparisons) (Figure 4). This can likely be explained by the large
499 variability in climate conditions, trophic state, sediment type and water level
500 fluctuations, within and between the different types of systems. Therefore, other factors
501 likely outplay differences arising from the type of aquatic system. As a consequence,
502 the contribution of CH₄ to the total GHG emission estimate did not significantly vary
503 among systems either; it ranged from 10% to 21% contribution to the total CO₂-eq
504 emission from dry inland waters (Figure 4).

505 Upscaling the mean dry inland water CH₄ flux rates from lakes, reservoirs,
506 ponds and streams according to their respective global surface areas revealed that $3.6 \pm$
507 0.4 (\pm standard error of the mean; SEM) Tg CH₄ evade from the dry sediments of inland
508 waters to the atmosphere annually (Table 3). This represents approximately 2.4% (\pm
509 0.2%; SEM) of the global CH₄ emission estimate attributed to water surfaces of lentic
510 and lotic inland water ecosystems ($0.15 \text{ Pg CH}_4 \text{ y}^{-1}$; Rosentreter et al., 2021).
511 Converting our cross-continental CH₄ emission from dry inland waters to C emission
512 indicates that CH₄ adds ~ 2.7 (± 0.3 ; SEM) Tg C y^{-1} (or 0.07%) to the current global C
513 emission estimate from inland waters (3.9 Pg C y^{-1} ; Drake et al., 2018) (Table 3).

514

515 **Figure 4** | Cross-continental mean CO₂-equivalent emission rates (CH₄ – blue; CO₂ –
516 red; g CO₂-eq m⁻² d⁻¹) from dry inland waters (far-right bar) divided by the different
517 types of aquatic systems (lakes, ponds, reservoirs, and streams). CO₂ flux measurements
518 were obtained from Keller et al. (2020) and were associated with the CH₄ flux
519 measurements collected at the same sampling sites. CH₄ fluxes were converted into
520 CO₂-equivalents by multiplying the mass-based CH₄ flux by 34, according to the 100-
521 year GWP (Myhre et al., 2013). Percentage values represent the contribution of each gas
522 to the cross-continental average emission rate in each type of aquatic system. Letter “a”
523 indicates no statistical difference in CH₄ contribution between the types of aquatic
524 systems.

525 **Table 3** | Cross-continental mean fluxes (\pm standard error of the mean; $\text{mg CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$) and cross-continental estimates of dry inland water CH_4
 526 emissions ($\text{Tg CH}_4 \text{ y}^{-1}$, $\text{Pg CO}_2\text{-eq y}^{-1}$, and Tg C y^{-1}) by different types of aquatic systems.

System type	Area of exposed aquatic sediments during one year ^a (km^2)	CH_4 emission rate ($\text{mg CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$)	Cross-continental CH_4 emission ($\text{Tg CH}_4 \text{ y}^{-1}$)	Cross-continental CH_4 emission in CO_2 equivalents ($\text{Pg CO}_2\text{-eq y}^{-1}$)	Cross-continental CH_4 emission as C emission (Tg C y^{-1})
Lakes and reservoirs	187,542 (Marcé et al., 2019)	44 ± 10.9	3.1 ± 0.7	0.1 ± 0.02	2.3 ± 0.5
Ponds	18,390 (Marcé et al., 2019)	38 ± 15.7	0.26 ± 0.1	0.009 ± 0.003	0.2 ± 0.08
Streams and rivers	84,461 (Raymond et al., 2013)	7 ± 5.6	0.21 ± 0.1	0.007 ± 0.006	0.16 ± 0.13
Total	290,393		3.6 ± 0.4	0.11 ± 0.01	2.7 ± 0.3

527 ^a *Seasonal and permanent exposure*

528 4. Conclusions, implications and future perspectives

529 This study provides the first cross-continental assessment of CH₄ fluxes from
530 dry inland waters based on *in situ* measurements. We found that 14% of the cross-
531 continental CO₂-eq emissions from dry inland waters can be attributed to CH₄. Our
532 estimate comes with uncertainties as the number of aquatic systems and climate zones
533 included in this study were non-uniformly represented (i.e., arid and polar regions were
534 not represented at all, and temperate zones were overrepresented), and given the large
535 variation in dry inland water CH₄ fluxes observed within the different types of aquatic
536 systems and climate zones studied here. Moreover, our estimates are solely related to
537 gaseous C species (CH₄ and CO₂) emissions and do not account for nitrous oxide (N₂O)
538 emissions which is an important GHG in these systems as well (Arce et al., 2018). In
539 addition, our global estimate of CH₄ emissions from dry inland waters may be an
540 underestimation because we likely underestimated the global surface area of dry inland
541 waters. While we used a surface area of 290,393 km² for our upscaling exercise, another
542 study that does not differentiate between types of aquatic systems and included
543 wetlands concluded that this area is considerably higher (806,321 km² – Pekel et al.
544 (2016)). Also, during our sampling, we likely generally missed emission peaks (i.e., hot
545 moments of emission) that can occur at the onset of drying (Jin et al., 2016;
546 Koschorreck, 2000; Kosten et al., 2018; Paranaíba et al., 2020). Ultimately, while our
547 estimates account for a good portion of the variability related to weather conditions
548 (since we sampled CH₄ fluxes and environmental parameters across a wide range of
549 locations and climate zones), our estimates do not consider CH₄ fluxes occurring under
550 extreme weather events (e.g., rainy days, snowy days), which therefore represents a
551 knowledge gap in this area of research and certainly deserves further research.

552 While the global CH₄ emission from dry inland waters may be small compared
553 to total aquatic (wet and dry, CO₂ and CH₄) emissions, for individual systems, CH₄
554 emission from dry sediments can be important (Jin et al., 2016). Dry inland-water
555 sediments occupy a temporally varying fraction of aquatic systems due to cycles of
556 rising and falling water levels. Hence, the contribution of dry-sediment CH₄, CO₂ and
557 N₂O emissions to the total emission also varies through time (Almeida et al., 2019; Arce
558 et al., 2018; Keller et al., 2021; Kosten et al., 2018; Paranaíba et al., 2020). The time-
559 integrated contribution of dry sediment to total inland water emissions is likely to
560 increase in the future as drought events are becoming more frequent and more intense.
561 As a result of this and ongoing widespread direct consumptive water uses, large areas of
562 marginal sediments from aquatic systems worldwide will be exposed to the atmosphere
563 (Pekel et al., 2016; Steward et al., 2012; Wurtsbaugh et al., 2017). We argue that future
564 work on aquatic GHG emissions needs to take CH₄, CO₂ and N₂O emissions from these
565 dynamic wet-dry regions into account in order to further improve our estimates of the
566 global GHG budget of inland waters. Such gained insights into the environmental
567 processes that produce and consume GHGs will enable improved predictions of changes
568 in atmospheric GHG concentrations under varying climate change scenarios.

569

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596

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599 **7. References**

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911

System type	CH ₄ flux (mg CH ₄ m ⁻² d ⁻¹)	Reference
Lakes (n = 45)		
<i>Dry sediment</i>	48 ± 91	
<i>Uphill soil</i>	1 ± 5	
Ponds (n = 16)		
<i>Dry sediment</i>	38 ± 63	
<i>Uphill soil</i>	0.3 ± 1	
Reservoirs (n = 19)		
<i>Dry sediment</i>	36 ± 78	This study
<i>Uphill soil</i>	2 ± 4	
Streams (n = 9)		
<i>Dry sediment</i>	7 ± 17	
<i>Uphill soil</i>	0.2 ± 0.7	
All systems (n = 89)		
<i>Dry sediment</i>	40 ± 80	
<i>Uphill soil</i>	1 ± 4	
Lake (Brazil)	1.4 ± 0.15 (<i>Amazonian floodplain</i>)	Koschorreck, 2000
Ponds (Spain)	4.8 ± 3.8 (<i>Dry bed</i>)	Obrador et al. 2018
Reservoir (Brazil)	0.9 ± 6.9 (<i>Drawdown</i>)	Amorim et al. 2019
Reservoir (China)	7 ± 8.9 (<i>Drawdown</i>)	Chen et al. 2011
Reservoir (China)	4 ± 1.5 (<i>Drawdown</i>)	Yang et al. 2012
Reservoir (China)	7.7 ± 5 (<i>Drawdown</i>)	Hao et al. 2019
Reservoir (Laos)	27 ± 36 (<i>Drawdown</i>)	Serça et al. 2016
Reservoir (Germany)	4.1 ^a (<i>Drawdown</i>)	Marcé et al. 2019
Reservoir (Germany)	7.2 ^a (<i>Drawdown</i>)	Marcé et al. 2019
Reservoir (Spain)	0 (<i>Drawdown</i>)	Marcé et al. 2019
Reservoir (Spain)	4.1 ^a (<i>Drawdown</i>)	Marcé et al. 2019
Reservoir (Spain)	0.3 ^a (<i>Drawdown</i>)	Marcé et al. 2019
Streams (United States)	0.4 ± 0.5 (<i>Dry river bed</i>)	Gallo et al. 2014
Streams (Spain)	3.2 ± 0.9 (<i>Dry river and impoundment beds</i>)	Gómez-Gener et al. 2015
Global CH₄ flux rates from surface waters (mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹)		
Lakes	153 ± 293	Rosentreter et al. 2021
Ponds	12 ± 30	Holgerson and Raymond 2016
Reservoirs	165 ± 369	Rosentreter et al. 2021
Streams	112 ± 425	Rosentreter et al. 2021

^a Mean values

Input variable	CH ₄ flux			
	β	<i>SE</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>CI</i>
(Intercept)	3.53	0.30	11.64	2.93 – 4.12
Interaction (Organic matter:Sediment temperature)	0.39	0.10	3.69	0.18 – 0.59
Organic matter	-0.54	0.15	-3.55	-0.85 – -0.24
Moisture	0.49	0.15	3.20	0.19 – 0.79
Conductivity	0.37	0.12	3.01	0.12 – 0.61
Elevation	0.35	0.17	1.98	0.004 – 0.7
Interaction (Moisture:Organic matter)	-0.20	0.10	-2.01	-0.41 – -0.006
R²m	0.23			
R²c	0.57			

System type	Area of exposed aquatic sediments during one year ^a	CH₄ emission rate	Cross-continental CH₄ emission	Cross-continental CH₄ emission in CO₂ equivalents	Cross-continental CH₄ emission as C emission
	(km²)	(mg CH₄ m⁻² d⁻¹)	(Tg CH₄ y⁻¹)	(Pg CO₂-eq y⁻¹)	(Tg C y⁻¹)
Lakes and reservoirs	187,542 (Marcé et al., 2019)	44 ± 10.9	3.1 ± 0.7	0.1 ± 0.02	2.3 ± 0.5
Ponds	18,390 (Marcé et al., 2019)	38 ± 15.7	0.26 ± 0.1	0.009 ± 0.003	0.2 ± 0.08
Streams and rivers	84,461 (Raymond et al., 2013)	7 ± 5.6	0.21 ± 0.1	0.007 ± 0.006	0.16 ± 0.13
Total	290,393		3.6 ± 0.4	0.11 ± 0.01	2.7 ± 0.3

^a *Seasonal and permanent exposure*

Figure 1

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Author contributions:

CRedit roles:

José R. Paranaíba: Conceptualization; Methodology; Software; Validation; Formal analysis; Investigation; Data curation; Writing - original draft; Writing - review & editing; Visualization;

Ralf Aben: Conceptualization; Methodology; Software; Validation; Investigation; Writing - review & editing; Visualization;

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